

UWB Aided Mobile Robot Localization with Neural Networks and the EKF*

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Abstract—This paper exploits the use of Ultra Wide Band (UWB) technology to improve the localization of robots in both indoor and outdoor environments. In order to efficiently integrate the UWB technology in existing multi-sensor architectures, such as Kalman-based, we propose two approaches to estimate the UWB position covariance values. The first approach uses statistical methods to estimate static covariance values based on data acquired a priori. The second approach adopts a neural network (NN) to capture the relationship between the positional error of the UWB data and the signal quality information, such as the Estimate Of Precision (EOP) and Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI). The GPS-RTK is used as ground truth and RGB-D odometry is adopted for both benchmarking and integration purposes. Position sources are fused by means of an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF). Real world experiments are conducted with a tracked mobile robot driving outdoors in a closed-loop trajectory. Results show that the NN is able to efficiently model the sensor covariances and adapt the trustworthiness of the EKF estimation, overcoming data loss by relying on the other available estimation source.

Index Terms—UWB, GPS-RTK, RGB-D, Robot Localization, EOP, RSSI, Covariance estimation, Neural Network, EKF

I. INTRODUCTION

Robots and automation are constantly introduced in our everyday lives ranging from indoor specific applications and outdoor services. In hybrid environments that require the robot to navigate in indoor paths and also the outdoors of a facility, it needs to be able to estimate its position relative to the infrastructure. This task is known as robot localization, which requires the robot to infer its location based on sensory input and keep track of it over time.

Ultra Wide Band is a wireless sensor system that comprises of anchor nodes and tag nodes. Tags are the tracked object from ranges of nearby anchors which are stationary. These sensors have been successfully applied within indoor environments [1], [2] and few works exist for outdoors [3]. They can be easily integrated within the infrastructure and

assist the robot's navigation process, by providing range measurements as part of the multilateration process. Many hybrid environments such as warehouses, public spaces, airports and hospitals have adopted robots for automating their processes by means of delivery and service robots [4].

In order to accomplish these functions, robots need to be aware of their surroundings and also track their location within the environment. This is a challenging task especially in hybrid environments, due to the added complexity in terms of the structure of the surroundings and mobility of humans. Indoor environments tend to be structured and well organised but outdoors this is not the case. It is unstructured and open to the weather changes and more prone to non linear phenomena.

Despite these difficulties, a method that is embedded within the infrastructure such as UWB devices, can provide a potential solution towards this direction [5]. The problem though is that as with every sensor, error is present in sensor measurements and can destabilise the robot's perception of location without prior modelling of its propagation over time. To mitigate this problem, filtering has been applied in the form of Kalman filters. For non linear cases the Extended Kalman Filter and Unscented Kalman filter have been applied successfully over the years [6], [7].

Within this work we investigate the noise of an unmodelled UWB sensor, from the position data and the signal quality information. As a first approach static covariance is calculated in the statistical sense. Then we deploy a neural network approach to identify patterns in the signal quality data and generate a dynamic covariance. As a final step we evaluate the position covariance values of the UWB by applying the EKF as a global state estimator for mobile robot localization and then compare the accuracy with GPS-RTK positioning.

II. RELATED WORK

In hybrid scenarios we require a sensor that is able to operate as equally well in both indoors and outdoors. The Global Positioning System (GPS) can not be used indoors and although feature based localization is useful indoors, achieving the same results outdoors is challenging, due to illumination variations and weather conditions which affect the scene recognition process.

Communication based approaches [8] avoid these challenges as the sensors are embedded within the infrastructure and deliver decimeter level precision as a localization source. Relevant technologies for this case are UWB [9], Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) [10], Bluetooth [11], WiFi [12] and Visible Light Communication (VLC) [13].

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The UWB communication channels [14] cover the lower and mid GHz region and their ranging capabilities can range from a few meters in indoor scenarios and extend to hundreds of meters in outdoor use cases. The physical principle is the signal time of flight (TOF) and position estimation can be performed according to the following range based variations: time of arrival (TOA), angle of arrival (AOA) and phase of arrival (POA)[15]. A detailed comparison of UWB for indoor positioning can be seen in [9], where examples of the applications are given and a comparison of hardware is performed in [16], where detailed experimental results and associated costs are presented.

Modelling position errors is a difficult process, due to sensor imperfections from their manufacture, sensor placement and measurement noise introduced by the operating environment [17]. It is essential to minimize the measurement uncertainty when estimating the robot state variables.

Kalman filters are capable of tracking a moving object's position in indoor environments [18] and outdoor environments [19] and correct the uncertainties of a robot's dynamical and measurement model. Covariances are required by the Extended Kalman Filter in order to perform the correction step of the filtering algorithm upon new position measurements.

This work contributes to the calculation of an unmodeled sensor's covariance and the integration of UWB for robot localization outdoors alongside RGB-D and IMU measurements. GPS-RTK serves as a groundtruth for comparison. Instead of computing the covariance numerically which is an intensive task, we have utilised a neural network to identify patterns in the data points of the robot trajectory, along with signal quality information and estimate suitable values for 2D position covariance. Finally we fuse the UWB, RGB-D and IMU data with an EKF to obtain the overall robot position, which can assist in outdoor GPS-denied environments.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section we describe the concepts involved within the work.

A. Mobile Robot System

Our robotic system consists of Red, Blue, Green and Depth (RGB-D) odometry [20], a real time framework that performs feature matching and detection from laser and image information with the use of a RANSAC algorithm [21]. It includes the loop closure function to recognise a scene that has been encountered before and correct the estimation of position. The measurements come from two 3D Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors¹ and a depth or as frequently mentioned point cloud camera² that provide us with the position information (x, y) and position covariances (C_x, C_y) which are dynamically calculated by this visual odometry method.

The orientation estimates of yaw, pitch and roll (α, β, γ) and the angular velocities $(\dot{\alpha}, \dot{\beta}, \dot{\gamma})$ are acquired from an

Fig. 1. System architecture, state variables along with the EKF for mobile robot localization using RGB-D, IMU, UWB information. GPS spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) are converted to Cartesian (x, y) via RTK and are not fused, but used as groundtruth. Position estimates are obtained from the RGB-D and UWB in Cartesian Cartesian (x, y) . Covariances are represented as (C_x, C_y) . Differentiation of sensor (yellow) and software (green) layer is used for scope clarity of the robot setup.

inertial measurement unit³ (IMU). The UWB points are converted to odometry data and the GPS is transformed from spherical coordinates to Cartesian, through the Real Time Kinematics (RTK)⁴ of the base station which is placed at our facilities. Finally all position information are fused within the EKF framework for localization as can be seen in Figure 1. The orientation information and angular velocities are intrinsically used in the EKF for completing the state vector. The UWB⁵ position and signal quality information are provided and the covariance estimation is the scope of this work.

B. Robot localization

Mobile robot localization [22] is the process of tracking the states of the system over time. The states refer to the pose information, such as translation (p_{xyz}) and orientation (o_{xyz}) . In general, full state vector of the mobile robotic system can be described by additional information such as linear (v_{xyz}) , angular (ω_{xyz}) velocities and linear acceleration (α_{xyz}) which are described by the robot's dynamic model and are represented as a 15 parameter state vector $x_k = [p_{xyz}, o_{xyz}, v_{xyz}, \omega_{xyz}, \alpha_{xyz}]$.

Sensor noise is present in the measurements and process noise in the dynamic model and is usually assumed to be Gaussian, but this is not always the case. External disturbances can influence the measurements of the system. In principle they are additive error to the process noise and non linear. The selection of reliable information for localization depend on the states with the least uncertainty and highest accuracy and availability.

³http://en.rion-tech.net/products_detail/productId=158.html

⁴<https://store.emlid.com/product/reachm-plus>

⁵<https://www.nooploop.com/en/>

¹<http://www.lslidar.com/en/mso/81>

²<https://www.intelrealsense.com/depth-camera-d435>

Multi-modal localization [23] refers to the use of various sensors, in terms of physical theory of operation and complement each other to either produce a full state estimation or correct a specific state variable with redundant state information. Sensor fusion [24] is the process of filtering the sensor inputs to derive a combined odometry source that is robust to disturbances and accumulative errors that can be utilized for tracking.

The Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) is a non linear state estimator that is able to predict the states of position by iterative comparison between the system model and the measurement model. This comparison acts as trust indicator for the selection of the most reliable source of information upon each measurement. Predictions are performed according to the system model or the measurement model. A final correction step is performed to reduce uncertainty of the predicted position based on the previous measurements and the independent odometry methods. This way we are able to fuse multiple sensor inputs into a single odometry source that we can use for tracking in the global reference frame. In our case, it is implemented within the robot localization [25] ROS package and has extensively been used in the robotics domain as a localization tool.

The full state vector's elements can be estimated directly or indirectly from sensor data. It is often hard to accurately keep track of all the state variables, due to inherent uncertainty in the measurements and the non linearities of the system's dynamic model. Other potential challenges are computational resources available onboard and different frequency update rates of the sensors. For the purpose of this work we only focus on the 2D positioning of the robotic platform as we are limited to the GPS-RTK position information which is 2D. We fuse the UWB $p_{uwb} = [x_{uwb}, y_{uwb}]$ as an absolute positioning source of information, with the aim to model its covariances and the RGB-D position measurements $p_{rgbd} = [x_{rgbd}, y_{rgbd}]$ and IMU data. The GPS-RTK position $p_{gps} = [x_{gps}, y_{gps}]$ is used as a ground truth indicator for comparison hence not used in the sensor fusion process.

C. Covariance estimation

Covariance [26] in sensor measurements represents the uncertainty of a state variable, such as the (X,Y) position coordinates of a robot in Cartesian space, which is the subject of the tracking process and minimization of its effect is mandatory. The covariance values are necessary requirement for any sensor within a sensor fusion framework.

The static position covariance is given by Equation 1 where n is the number of trajectory points and (x,y) are the coordinates of the robotic system and μ_x and μ_y their means. Since the robot is a single entity we calculate the covariance of the trajectory travelled, where there is dependency or correlation between them.

$$Cov_{(x,y)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{(x_i - \mu_x)(y_i - \mu_y)} \quad (1)$$

With Equation 1, we are able to compute the lower bound for covariance. After further observation by increasing the

Fig. 2. The mobile robotic system. It consists of two 3D LiDAR, a pointcloud camera, GPS-RTK and the UWB tag sensor.

covariance for each coordinate to higher values we observed that the convergence of the EKF output could be improved until an upper bound value which was found experimentally and describes the scenario of the UWB odometry, diverging from the ground truth trajectory. Static EKF covariances were insufficient because we observed large data gaps in the data, and no compensation was applied for the temporary loss of the sensor input as described in the next section.

D. Shallow Neural Network

A neural network (NN) approach was adopted to fit the trajectory data (as a regression problem) and Bayesian Regularization was used for training to deal with the noisy nature of the data similar to [27]. The model was trained with the estimation of precision (EOP) and received signal strength indicator (RSSI) transmit (Tx) and receive (Rx) parameters, leading to a three feature input vector $q_k = [eop_{xyz}, rssi_{rx}, rssi_{tx}]$. The NN consists of a single layer network of 100 nodes and the number of epochs was set to 1000 to avoid over fitting the training dataset.

The EOP is based on the mathematical relationships of the multi-anchor setup as of Figure 3 and it is provided by the Tag sensor. The lower the value the higher the accuracy of the position estimation. To elaborate, if a value of EOP in the x-axis is 0.3 meters, then the coordinate deviation of the UWB tag along the X axis may be ± 0.3 m. The maximum values for the EOP along all three axes is 2.55m, which means that the positioning accuracy is around 2.55m according to the sensor's manual documentation.

The RSSI [28] is an index of the UWB signal quality and is measured as the first signal path between the anchor and tag and also as the total path, between the anchors. This parameter is used to evaluate the signal strength quality as perceived from the tag in accordance to the anchors. In our case we have the rx and tx RSSI as reported by the tag.

The output, or response, of the NN was defined by the squared error between the ground truth odometry provided by

the GPS-RTK and the UWB odometry. This is an assumption taking into account that the covariances could be proportional to the localization squared error, similar to the experiments in [29]. The proportionality of the tracking error was found experimentally, by changing the static values of the (x, y) covariances of the UWB between lower and upper bound and observing the behaviour of the EKF output.

The NN was used to dynamically inflate the covariance of the robot's position in uncertain scenarios, such as signal loss and under the influence of process noise, hence affecting the fusion process of the EKF. The inflation is in the form of scalar values of 100000 for the EOP and -100000 for the RSSI. These values are apparently erroneous for signal quality and the NN produces appropriate position covariances based on them. The values of UWB $[Cx, Cy]$ are constrained between a lower static value and a maximum static value as discussed in the next section.

The philosophy behind this approach is that when we receive poor signal quality from the UWB sensor or large fluctuations due to external disturbances, the robot should reduce its trust in the UWB measurements and rely more on the most recent position estimate of the RGB-D odometry, while still creating the robot trajectory over time.

E. Performance Metrics

As a trajectory metric, we are using the Euclidean distance (ED) which represents the distance between the odometry points and the ground truth reference. The formula is described by Equation 2 and it represents the linear difference between the ground truth $p_{gt} = [x_{gt}, y_{gt}]$ and another positioning source's $p_s = [x_s, y_s]$ measurements. The x and y represent the coordinates of the two sources for the overall trajectory.

$$dist(x, y) = \sqrt{(x_{gt} - x_s)^2 + (y_{gt} - y_s)^2} \quad (2)$$

The trajectory standard deviation is given by Equation 3, where the x and y are the Cartesian coordinates of the robot trajectory and their mean values μ_x and μ_y . It is a measure of how far apart from the ground truth mean are the compared position points. In our case the ground truth considered is the GPS-RTK and the compared positioning sources are the UWB, RGB-D and EKF trajectory points.

$$S(x, y) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \mu_x)^2 + (y_i - \mu_y)^2} \quad (3)$$

IV. RESULTS

A. Ultra Wide Band setup

UWB is a wireless system that consists of a distributed set of anchors placed across a predefined application area. For our experiment we are using the LinkTrack UWB sensors, which offer long range communication which is around 500 meters, fast update rates of 50Hz per sensor and software compatible with the Robot operating System (ROS)⁶. The

Fig. 3. The UWB setup outdoors: Anchors A0-A5 that provide the ranges to T0 which is placed on the robot. The UWB envelope is the rectangular area of highest positioning accuracy.

communication of the tag T0 on the robot is at 921600 baud over USB connection. The multilateration⁷ software runs at 1KHz and provides the position and signal quality (EOP, RSSI) parameters at a high acquisition rate.

The experimental setup consists of six fixed anchors and one mobile tag. We have configured the anchors with id's A0-A5 and the tag as T0. The position of the anchors can be seen in Table I and are automatically generated as part of the sensor calibration process on startup, by inter anchor communication and the coordinates of all anchors are stored in A0.

All anchors have a clear line of sight and the global coordinate system is created based on the placement of A0 which is the origin. The coordinates of all consecutive anchors are measured in relation to the origin. We have distributed them in an approximate rectangular geometry which can be seen in Figure 3.

TABLE I
UWB ANCHOR POSITIONS

	X(m)	Y(m)
A0	0	0
A1	-0.313	21.363
A2	6.91	22.657
A3	9.731	0
A4	-0.25	9.92
A5	8.498	10.068

B. Experimental data

The experiment was performed outdoors by navigating within the UWB envelope and completing seven laps. The robot was teleoperated for ease of maneuverability as we recorded the positioning information from the UWB, RGB-D

⁶<https://www.ros.org/>

⁷https://github.com/nooploop-dev/nlink_parser

and GPS-RTK. For comparison purposes we have considered as ground truth reference the GPS data as it is the most reliable source of information on the robot with update rate of 5 Hz and a positioning accuracy of 0.5 cm when static and 0.7 cm when moving. This decision was made in spite of the inherent error in the GPS information, but is based on the following fact. We estimate the GPS-RTK odometry only when it is in fixed status and its signal quality is ensured. Under these conditions non-fix data will not be available within the system for measurement purposes.

C. Static Covariance performance

The values for static covariance were computed from the existing trajectories by Equation 1 and were found to be 0.0015 for the x and y coordinates. After placing these values for the covariance of $[Cx, Cy]$ we observed the trajectories of Figure 4, where the EKF considers the UWB as the most trustworthy sensor input. Although initially promising we observed fluctuations to the trajectory that are due to the high frequency rate of the signal acquisition and also the instability of traversing uneven terrain. The maximum value of the static covariance was found to be 25, after directly manipulating the values and is the case of diversion of the EKF from the ground truth trajectory.

A major hurdle that we observed were gaps in data once and then that have a huge impact on localization. During the 4th and 6th lap, we observed the largest gaps in data and are visible in Figure 4. These gaps were unidentified and we concluded that the cause is firmware related after looking into the UWB sensor setup.

Despite these errors, we did not observe a shift of the EKF to the RGB-D information, as it still trusted the UWB input as the most reliable source, and as a result creates a trajectory at the last recorded point, until the signal is recovered.

This behaviour is not suitable for localization despite the RGB-D odometry being available for corrections. Hence our approach of developing the NN to identify signal loss and large fluctuations in the trajectory is sought as a viable option.

D. Dynamic Covariance performance

With the use of the neural network we were able to model the evolution of the process noise over time, even in scenarios where no data was published from the UWB sensors. We based this approach on training the shallow NN on the EOP and RSSI values of the UWB signal, as reported by the tag T0. The total data are 3860 position measurements that represent the seven laps of the robot trajectory.

The data consist of the positions from sensor measurements $p_{uwb} = [x_{uwb}, y_{uwb}]$, has been divided into three sets using random indices: (i) 75% for training to compute the gradient and updating the network weights and biases; (ii) 5% for validation whose error is monitored during the training process and allows to save the network weights and biases whenever a minimum is reached; and (iii) 20% for testing, which is used after training and to assess the performance of the proposed approach.

Fig. 4. EKF with static UWB covariance, where the data loss is at the bottom left quarter of the trajectory of the 6th lap as a discontinuity of the cyan trajectory.

Since the recorded data have imperfections that are representative of the actual robot working in the outdoor environment, the model was able to predict appropriate covariance values for the 2D position based on the trajectory performed and the signal quality of the UWB at each measurement step prior to the EKF prediction step.

The estimated dynamic covariance values are used as a trust indicator from the EKF to either consider the UWB as reliable source or rely more on the RGB-D odometry for localization.

The response of the EKF can be seen in Figure 5. The location where signal loss occurs is highlighted in the gray box area, and the EKF maintained the trajectory tracking based on the RGB-D odometry source without losing track of the robot's trajectory (in cyan) over time. An additional remark is that the filtered odometry follows the ground truth trajectory with a slight offset in the y axis which is due to the UWB anchor geometry imperfections.

A comparison with Figure 4 reveals the difference of having static versus dynamic covariance, as the trajectory in the first case (in black) is halted and the EKF does not converge to the RGB-D at all. It only recovers when signal is again available, without keeping track of the robot (in cyan) and it can be observed as stationary for this duration, at the last available UWB measurement. It clearly can be seen that the localization with the dynamic approach keeps track of the robot over time, flagging the UWB as unreliable information for the duration of data loss. For the duration of the robot trajectory the UWB behaviour was smoother compared to the original signal with minimal deviations due to the high acquisition rate.

The EKF acknowledges the UWB as an unreliable source of odometry for this duration and hence relies on the RGB-D odometry and continues to track the position of the robot until the UWB sensor information is again available as can

Fig. 5. EKF with dynamic UWB covariance during the 6th and 7th lap where the presence of no data is highlighted in the gray box.

be seen in the top half of Figure 6.

The RGB-D odometry, in purple color, is shifted and this is due to the drift over time. Moreover, the errors for the individual positioning methods have been calculated by the Euclidean distance according to Equation 2 and can be seen plotted at the bottom of Figure 6. The drift over time is depicted in the upward trend of the error over time in green color. Large data gaps of the UWB during the fourth and the highlighted sixth lap are clearly visible in blue as spikes and despite their occurrence were tackled due to the dynamic covariance, leading to a functional overall robot localization with the UWB sensor.

Regarding the results, Table II summarises the Euclidean distance followed by the standard deviation of each odometry source with reference to the GPS-RTK positioning information. The individual positioning methods remain the same as we are manipulating the position covariance and not the actual position information. The UWB average error is 0.2974 m with a deviation of 0.8322 m and is common in both cases as we are not affecting the raw measurements of the sensor. For the RGBD odometry the value is at 0.982 m with a standard deviation of 0.7117 m. As previously stated visual methods are prone to drift hence the large error over time unless compensated by the IMU. Finally the EKF error is 0.1336 m with a deviation of 0.0681 m which is better compared to the static case, where the error is 0.2956 m with a standard deviation of 0.8275 m.

TABLE II

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS COMPARED TO GPS-RTK AND TRAJECTORY DEVIATIONS

Odometry	Static	Dynamic
	Mean ED / STD	Mean ED / STD
UWB	0.2974 ± 0.8322 m	0.2974 ± 0.8322 m
RGB-D	0.9823 ± 0.7117	0.9823 ± 0.7117 m
EKF	0.2956 ± 0.8275 m	0.1336 ± 0.0681 m

Fig. 6. Euclidean distance of UWB, RGB-D and EKF compared with GPS-RTK and the focus on the error of the UWB of the 6th and an example of transient error on the 7th lap. The EKF compensation due to the dynamic covariance can be observed, in cyan color, and the trajectory is completed with RGB-D odometry influence.

V. CONCLUSION

Within this work, we demonstrated the effectiveness of modelling the UWB sensor covariances with a NN approach by thoroughly comparing the behavior of the robot's localization and monitoring its response, under disturbances and lack of data. All in all, the neural network approach is more tolerant under uncertainty and is capable of assisting the Kalman filter in selecting an alternative odometry source for position correction. This aids the localization capabilities of a mobile robot outdoors and can definitely be included in hybrid environments and in GPS denied environments, where signal loss is a reality and complement the overall localization framework as an additional absolute positioning source of estimation.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Poulou, Z. Emersic, O. Steven Eyobu, and D. Seog Han, "An accurate indoor user position estimator for multiple anchor uwb localization," in *2020 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC)*, 2020, pp. 478–482.
- [2] A. Ren, F. Zhou, A. Rahman, X. Wang, N. Zhao, and X. Yang, "A study of indoor positioning based on uwb base-station configurations," in *2017 IEEE 2nd Advanced Information Technology, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (IAEAC)*, 2017, pp. 1939–1943.
- [3] J. Fernandez-Madriral, E. Cruz-Martin, J. Gonzalez, C. Galindo, and J. Blanco, "Application of uwb and gps technologies for vehicle localization in combined indoor-outdoor environments," in *2007 9th International Symposium on Signal Processing and Its Applications*, 2007, pp. 1–4.

- [4] Y. Shen, D. Guo, F. Long, L. A. Mateos, H. Ding, Z. Xiu, R. B. Hellman, A. King, S. Chen, C. Zhang, and H. Tan, "Robots under covid-19 pandemic: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 1590–1615, 2021.
- [5] A. Poulouse, O. S. Eyobu, M. Kim, and D. S. Han, "Localization error analysis of indoor positioning system based on uwb measurements," in *2019 Eleventh International Conference on Ubiquitous and Future Networks (ICUFN)*, 2019, pp. 84–88.
- [6] S. Yang and H. Li, "Application of ekf and ukf in target tracking problem," in *2016 8th International Conference on Intelligent Human-Machine Systems and Cybernetics (IHMSC)*, vol. 01, 2016, pp. 116–120.
- [7] E. Wan and R. Van Der Merwe, "The unscented kalman filter for non-linear estimation," in *Proceedings of the IEEE 2000 Adaptive Systems for Signal Processing, Communications, and Control Symposium (Cat. No.00EX373)*, 2000, pp. 153–158.
- [8] K. Meena, M. Gupta, and A. Kumar, "Analysis of uwb indoor and outdoor channel propagation," in *2020 IEEE International Women in Engineering (WIE) Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering (WIECON-ECE)*, 2020, pp. 352–355.
- [9] L. Zwirello, T. Schipper, M. Jalilvand, and T. Zwick, "Realization limits of impulse-based localization system for large-scale indoor applications," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 39–51, 2015.
- [10] A. Buffi, P. Nepa, and R. Cioni, "Sarfid on drone: Drone-based uhfrfid tag localization," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on RFID Technology Application (RFID-TA)*, 2017, pp. 40–44.
- [11] S. G. Obreja and A. Vulpe, "Evaluation of an indoor localization solution based on bluetooth low energy beacons," in *2020 13th International Conference on Communications (COMM)*, 2020, pp. 227–231.
- [12] M. Xue, W. Sun, H. Yu, H. Tang, A. Lin, X. Zhang, and R. Zimmermann, "Locate the mobile device by enhancing the wifi-based indoor localization model," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 8792–8803, 2019.
- [13] Q. Liang and M. Liu, "A tightly coupled vlc-inertial localization system by ekf," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 3129–3136, 2020.
- [14] P. Kaniewski, J. Kazubek, and T. Kraszewski, "Application of uwb modules in indoor navigation system," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Microwaves, Antennas, Communications and Electronic Systems (COMCAS)*, 2017, pp. 1–5.
- [15] Y. Cheng and T. Zhou, "Uwb indoor positioning algorithm based on tdoa technology," in *2019 10th International Conference on Information Technology in Medicine and Education (ITME)*, 2019, pp. 777–782.
- [16] A. R. Jiménez Ruiz and F. Seco Granja, "Comparing ubisense, bespoon, and decawave uwb location systems: Indoor performance analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 66, no. 8, pp. 2106–2117, 2017.
- [17] D. B. Jourdan, D. Dardari, and M. Z. Win, "Position error bound for uwb localization in dense cluttered environments," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 44, no. 2, pp. 613–628, 2008.
- [18] Christiant, Y.-C. Lee, W. Yu, and J. Cho, "Augmented ekf localization for mobile robots in urban environments," in *2010 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics*, 2010, pp. 986–991.
- [19] Christiant, Y.-C. Lee, and W. Yu, "Ekf localization with lateral distance information for mobile robots in urban environments," in *2011 8th International Conference on Ubiquitous Robots and Ambient Intelligence (URAI)*, 2011, pp. 281–286.
- [20] M. Labbé and F. Michaud, "Rtab-map as an open-source lidar and visual simultaneous localization and mapping library for large-scale and long-term online operation," *Journal of Field Robotics*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 416–446, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/rob.21831>
- [21] W. Wei, H. Jun, and T. Yiping, "Image matching for geomorphic measurement based on sift and ransac methods," in *2008 International Conference on Computer Science and Software Engineering*, vol. 2, 2008, pp. 317–320.
- [22] J. Krejsa and S. Vechet, "Fusion of local and global sensory information in mobile robot outdoor localization task," in *2018 18th International Conference on Mechatronics - Mechatronika (ME)*, 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [23] D. Lee, S. Son, K. Yang, J. Park, and H. Lee, "Sensor fusion localization system for outdoor mobile robot," in *2009 ICCAS-SICE*, 2009, pp. 1384–1387.
- [24] H. Agarwal, P. Tiwari, and R. G. Tiwari, "Exploiting sensor fusion for mobile robot localization," in *2019 Third International conference on I-SMAC (IoT in Social, Mobile, Analytics and Cloud) (I-SMAC)*, 2019, pp. 463–466.
- [25] T. Moore and D. Stouch, "A generalized extended kalman filter implementation for the robot operating system," in *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Intelligent Autonomous Systems (IAS-13)*. Springer, July 2014.
- [26] J. Sequeira, A. Tsourdos, and S. Lazarus, "Robust covariance estimation in sensor data fusion," in *2009 IEEE International Workshop on Safety, Security Rescue Robotics (SSRR 2009)*, 2009, pp. 1–7.
- [27] H. Xu and J. J. Collins, "Estimating the odometry error of a mobile robot by neural networks," in *2009 International Conference on Machine Learning and Applications*, 2009, pp. 378–385.
- [28] J. Du, J.-F. Diouris, and Y. Wang, "A rssi based parameter tracking strategy for constrained position localization," *EURASIP journal on advances in signal processing*, vol. 2017, 11 2017.
- [29] Y. Eldar, "Minimum mean-squared error covariance shaping," in *2003 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing*, vol. 6, 05 2003, pp. VI – 713.